

ANALYSIS OF PILGRIMAGE VISIT MOTIVES IN DKI JAKARTA

Meri Oktaviani¹, Sari Narulita¹, Ahmad Hakam¹

¹Islamic Studies Department, Social Sciences Faculty, Universitas Negeri Jakarta

merioktaviani_jai15@mahasiswa.unj.ac.id.com,

sari-narulita@unj.ac.id, ahmad-hakam@unj.ac.id

Abstract

Tomb of Habib Husein bin Abu Bakar Alaydrus is one of the spiritual tourism destinations visited by many tourists, both local and foreign tourists. The number of tourists who come to the tomb of the Luar Batang approximately is 10,000 pilgrims every week. Pilgrims who come are not only Muslims but also non-Muslims. Generally, non-Muslim visitors enter from the side of the Luar Batang Mosque. This article is trying to review the motives of visitors who visit Luar Batang tomb based on observations and interviews with visitors from all folks of life. The results of this study are the mapping of the motives of visitors in doing a pilgrimage tour so that it can be analyzed and developed by other religious tourism destinations.

DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.2549125

1. Introduction

Islam is a world religion, culture, and civilization that has entered Indonesia since the 17th century. Its presence on the Indonesian archipelago has contributed significantly to the diversity of cultures in Indonesia. Apart from that, Islam has also enriched plurality with the Islamization of culture which gave birth to small traditions in various regions in Indonesia such as Sunda, Java, Aceh, Sasak, Malay, Bugis, and others. One of the cultural features that contribute to the Islamic tradition in Indonesia is the tradition of pilgrimage to the graves of saints, and people who are considered sacred.

The phenomenon of pilgrimage always exists in every people throughout its history, which is not only done by Muslims but other religious people. Communities in Indonesia themselves have long known the pilgrimage tradition. According to J.J. Fox in his article entitled "Pilgrimage Visit to the Tombs of Guardians, the founder of Islam on Java" said, the tradition of pilgrimage to sacred graves has long been carried out by the Indonesian Islamic community, both by well-known leaders and common people. This tradition is valid as an Islamic culture because their rituals are escorted by an all-Islamic procession, except for a few questionable things.

Pilgrimage activities in Indonesia have a wide variety of professions. It is also understandable that the critical pilgrimage is a theological understanding derived from Sufism. The teachings of Sufism illustrate someone who has *karomah* or a person who has blessings and can give *syafaah* (help) for pilgrims. Therefore there are many graves, be it the *ulama*, the hero of Islam, or the person who contributed to his time, that become the destination of the pilgrim visitors.

The word *ziarah* is an absorption word from the Arabic word *ziyarah*. This word means a visit, either to a living person or even a deceased person. While technically, this word indicates a series of activities of visiting certain tombs, such as the Tomb of the Prophet, Guardians, Heroes, Parents, Relatives, and others. Pilgrimage is a religious calling to remind two things,

namely the life of the person being visited, and the consequences of the actions carried out the next day.

Pilgrimage is also a practice that aims to look closely at historical places and to witness real essential places in the development of Islamic religion, in order to strengthen faith. Pilgrimage activities can be carried out by both individuals and groups. At present, there are also many religious study assemblies or majelis taklim that hold regular pilgrimage activities with various pilgrimage places visited in Indonesia. There are also those who are alone or small families who deliberately visit only to make a pilgrimage. DKI Jakarta is one of the cities that has a variety of historic grave sites and is also much in demand by the community, both local and outside the region. The tomb in DKI Jakarta which has the most interest and has become one of the cultural heritage, namely the Luar Batang tomb. Every day the Luar Batang tomb of the trunk is never empty of visitors. Especially on special days such as Haul, Maulid Nabi, Isra 'Mi'raj, and Thursday night. Pilgrims usually come from a variety of different social backgrounds, both local and out-of-area and there are also those from overseas such as Malaysia, Singapore, etc. They came to make a pilgrimage and offered prayers at the tomb to get various blessings according to their respective goals. Starting from the blessing of sustenance, the blessing of age, and also to improve the spirituality of themselves.

This phenomenon is an interesting for researchers. To analyze and examine what motivations or driving factors that cause visitors to make the pilgrimage. That indeed will not be separated from various things that motivate them. The term motivation comes from English, namely motivation. However, the original word is a motive that has also been used in the Malay language, the word motif, which means the goal or all efforts to encourage someone to do something. Whereas in language Motivation is a driving force that results in a member of the organization willing to mobilize skills in the form of expertise or energy, skills and the time to carry out various activities. Which are his responsibility and fulfill his obligations, in order to achieve the goals and objectives of the organization that have been determined previously. Not much different according to Martin Handoko in his book "Motivation to Drive Behavior," motivation is a force or factor that is contained in humans, which gives rise, directs and organizes behavior.

Among the motivations that encourage someone to do something, there are two types of motivation:

1) Intrinsic motivation

The motives that become active function do not need to be stimulated from the outside, because in each there is an urge to do something. For example, someone who likes to exercise, there is no need for someone to exercise or encourage him; he has been diligent in exercising.

2) Extrinsic motivation

The motives are active and functioning because of external stimuli. For example, someone eats because of hunger; a motorbike driver wears a helmet for fear of being given a police ticket, a student wears shoes when he enters the class.

Based on the above understanding it can be concluded that motivation is the driving force of a person to carry out specific activities in order to achieve the goals. In carrying out every human activity, it will never be separated from the motive or motivating factors, both intrinsic and extrinsic factors which cause them to carry out specific activities. Likewise, by conducting pilgrimage, there is indeed a motive that encourages it, both from within oneself and from through influences that come from outside.

This study uses a qualitative approach, where researchers explore the depth of data obtained based on interviews, observation, and documentation. So that the data obtained will be

valid for analysis. This research data includes primary and secondary data. Primary data is obtained directly through in-depth interviews with visitors to the pilgrimage. While secondary data comes from the documentation, written sources or books that review motivation in making a pilgrimage. After the entire data has been collected, then it will be analyzed with descriptive-qualitative analysis techniques which are then broken down into a narrative.

2. Discussion

Based on the results of the study several motivations motivated visitors to make pilgrimage activities. Here are some motivations (goals) of pilgrims who became respondents in this study:

1. To Get Blessings

Most of the respondents said that they made a pilgrimage to get blessings. The blessing itself has various meanings. Some respondents understand blessings as excellent and calm in their lives. So that with his pilgrimage activities his heart will feel peaceful and comfortable in living the hustle and bustle of life. Other respondents understand blessings as life's welfare and happiness. By making a pilgrimage, they hopes that Allah will facilitate sustenance in his life. There are also those who understand blessing as a quick answer to prayer through wasilah (intermediary). Most of the pilgrims believe that by making the guardians or people who are considered pious, it is to be aware of the intention and prayer to Allah SWT.

2. Improve spirituality

For humans, spirituality is one of the dominant forces in meeting the needs of life that are not only related to biological or physical. They believe that spirituality can provide a sense of tranquility and comfort in the human soul. When dealing with various problems, one's self-spirituality dramatically influences the mental state that is being experienced by that person. The higher the level of spirituality will undoubtedly tend to do positive things rather than negative things.

It is also one of the objectives of the pilgrims to perform pilgrimage activities. Some respondents stated that they made a pilgrimage to fill and improve their religious spirituality. This motivation is closely related to human needs both psychologically and spiritually. In addition to human biological needs, also need to fill their psychological needs. So they life they live becomes more balanced. By taking the time to make a pilgrimage, they feel that the mental emptiness that initially was so disturbing was lost. So that most respondents, felt that after they made a pilgrimage. Their hearts felt lighter and more prepared in facing various problems.

3. Religious tourism

Currently, tourism activities are not only carried out in adrenaline, open nature, or other modern tourist attractions. However, many people make Islamic historical sites such as the graves of guardians as tourism activities to fill their time off. Many people today are looking for tourist destinations that not only provide physical satisfaction but provide the inner or spiritual satisfaction that can provide positive energy. One of them is a pilgrimage which is currently one of the destinations for religious tourism. Jakarta is one of the cities that has many pilgrimage destinations with visitors to pilgrimages from various regions. Many of the recitation assemblies held special events for pilgrimage tours, both in order to fill holiday activities, introduce the graves of the guardians, the scholars, or Islamic heroes in Jakarta. Like the Ummul Battul recitation assembly which was pioneered by Ustadzah Aisyah BSA, every year she always held Pilgrimage for Muslimah. She did this to provide entertainment to the worshippers, but with religious nuances that are still thick and can provide new energy.

4. Routines (Habits)

Routines are activities that are continuously carried out regularly and do not change to achieve specific goals. For some respondents, pilgrimage is an activity that has become their consumption continuously. In the sense that they make a pilgrimage because they are accustomed and have become routine activities carried out in their lives.

Some respondents said that they often conduct pilgrimage because it has become a routine or habit among their family and environment, both from childhood and adolescence. Even some respondents have regular schedules for pilgrimage. Like Missis Mrs. Suadah , Mrs. Nafsiah, and other family who visit the Luar Batang Tomb. Every Thursday night they always make a pilgrimage to the Luar Batang tomb. Certainly did not stop there; some respondents tried to apply the habit of making pilgrimages to their children to get to know the tombs of the guardians, the Scholars, and fighters who crossed the Islamic shari'a.

5. Pray for prayer

Lafaz al-wasilah generally covers two things. First; pleading with the goodness of the Prophets and those who were pious, both during their lives and after they died. Second; plead with good deeds ordered by God, which he has done.

According to Ibn Katsir in the book of commentary wasilah is a means that leads to the achievement of the goal. Wasilah is also nature (place name) which is the highest in heaven, which is the position and residence of the Messenger of Allah. in heaven. That is the place in heaven that is closest to y Throne.

In this case, pray the intended prayer is that the trustees or scholars also have the message that can provide intercession for those who pray for him. The pilgrims also believed that by making pilgrimages and praying for the grave experts, the grave experts would also pray for them so Allah will quickly granted their intentions. In this case, the pilgrims do not ask the grave expert but still pray to Allah through the preaching of the guardians or the scholars who are a pilgrimage.

This is one of the driving factors or goals of pilgrims to make a pilgrimage. In this case, they believe that by making pilgrimages to the Muslim Scholars or the saints, their hopes or aspirations will quickly reach Allah or granted quickly

Some non-Muslims also visited grave sites in the Jakarta area. One of the tombs that became its destination was the Luar Batang. Non-Muslim visitors usually have different motives in visiting graves, including:

1. To search for research data

Some non-Muslims came to Luar Batang's grave to conduct research. In this case, non-Muslims come to the tomb to find data related to the research they are working on. Because they are outside of religion, many made pilgrimages even though in different ways.

2. Expanding knowledge

Some visitors from non-Muslim background come to expand knowledge both related to Islamic culture, as well as cultural heritage sites in Indonesia that influence the community. Those are some of the motivations of non-Muslim pilgrim visitors who also visit graves in the DKI Jakarta area, especially the Luar Batang Tomb.

The results of the study shows that there are several motivations or motivating factors of why pilgrims make pilgrimages to graves in Indonesia, especially in Jakarta. It is indeed very influenced by several factors, both factors within oneself and external factors. In this study,

intrinsic and extrinsic factors influence each other. In addition to the influence from within themselves, the pilgrims were also influenced by external factors which make them willing or motivated to make a visit to the tomb to achieve their goal.

3. CONCLUSION

From the explanation above it can be concluded that there are several motivations or goals of pilgrims in conducting pilgrimage activities. Each pilgrim has different motivations or goals in conducting pilgrimage activities. The results of study show that the motivation of the pilgrims in conducting pilgrimage includes: First, to get blessings, and the blessing in here has different meanings. Second, to increase spirituality.

Pilgrims visit the tomb because of personal encouragement or spiritual reason that makes them want to make a pilgrimage. Third, religious tourism where pilgrims conduct a pilgrimage to fill their time off with activities that can draw closer to Allah SWT. Besides that, the pilgrims also came to see how the architecture and beauty of the pilgrimage place. Fourth, the routine is a habit that is continuously carried out and has become a habit both in the family and the neighborhood. Moreover, the last one is Wasilah prayer, where pilgrims make pilgrimages to achieve hopes or aspirations through wasilah (intermediaries) those who are close to Allah such as prophets, saints, religious scholars, or pious people. Even though these people are no longer in the world, the pilgrims believe that the closeness of the righteous people to Allah will deliver the fulfillment of prayer. Therefore many of the pilgrims are motivated to make a pilgrimage to achieve their hopes and aspirations.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We would like to show the gratitude and the appreciation to the Ministry of Research and Higher Education and State University of Jakarta who has provided assistance and support in conduction the research. lastly, thanks to the religious tourism research team who played a role in enriching this study

References

- [1] Balai Pelestarian Peninggalan Purbakala Jawa Tengah. (2006). *Jejak Para Wali dan Ziarah Spiritual*. Jakarta: Kompas Media Nusantara.
- [2] Khumaeroh, U., Narulita, S., & Aulia, R. N. (2017). The Improvement of Intrapersonal Communication Through Religious Tourism. *Proceedings International Conference on Media Studies* (pp. 419 – 425). Malaysia: UUM Malaysia.
- [3] [Http://isma-ismi.com/pengertianmotivasi.html](http://isma-ismi.com/pengertianmotivasi.html) . (2015, 01 10).
- [4] Abidin, Z. (1991). *Alam Kubur dan Seluk Beluknya*. Solo: Rineka Cipta.
- [5] Am, S. (n.d.). *Interaksi dan motivasi Belajar Mengajar.*, (pp. 73-74).
- [6] Balai Pelestarian Peninggalan Purbakala Jawa Tengah. (2006). *Jejak Para Wali dan Ziarah Spiritual*. Jakarta: Kompas Media Nusantara.
- [7] Departemen Agama RI. (1994). Jakarta.
- [8] Fox, J. (1991). *Ziarah Visit To The Tombs of Wali, The Founder of Islam on Java*” dalam M.C. Ricklefs (ed), *Islam in Indonesian Social Context*. Melbourne: CSEAS Monash University.

- [9] Handoko, M. (1992). *Motivasi Penggerak Tingkah Laku*. Yogyakarta: Kanisius.
- [10] Karyono, H. A. (1997). *Kepariwisata*. Jakarta: PT. Grsindo.
- [11] Narulita, S., Aulia, R. N., Wajdi, F., & Khumaeroh, U. (2017). Pembentukan Karakter Religius Melalui Wisata Religi. *Prosiding Seminar Nasional Tahunan Fakultas Ilmu Sosial Universitas Negeri Medan*, 1, p. 166.
- [12] P.Siagian, S. (n.d.). *Teori Motivasi dan Aplikasinya*.
- [13] Rahmawati, H. (2016). Motivasi Daya Tarik Wisatawan Religi Di Astana Mangadeg (Studi Kasus di Astana Mangadeg, Kecamatan Matesih, Kabupaten Karanganyar). *Jurnal Sosiologi DILEMA*, 31.
- [14] Ruslan, A. (2007). *Ziarah Wali Spiritual Sepanjang Masa*. Yogyakarta : Pustaka Timur.
- [15] Siregar, S. (n.d.). *Ibadah Agung Yang Banyak Terselewengkan*.
- [16] Syaikh, A. b. (2008). *Tafsir Ibnu Katsir*, pen.M.Abdul Ghoffar (3 ed.). Jakarta: Pustaka Imam Syafi'i.

